

Review articles

To “Gap Year” or not to “Gap Year” Before Medical School? A Shakespearean Question of Benefits, Challenges, and Opportunities.

Patrick J Soonthornprapuet, BS¹, Elis A Kristo, College Student, Class of 2026², Nicholas Burns, BS³, Patrick B Oneal, MD, FACS^{1,4}, Gentian Kristo, MD, MPH, FACS^{1,5}

¹ Surgery, VA Boston Healthcare System, ² Neuroscience, Boston College, ³ The Master’s in Medical Sciences Program, Boston University, ⁴ Surgery, Boston Medical Center, ⁵ Surgery, Brigham and Women’s Hospital

Keywords: medical school admission, gap years, pre-medical students, post-collegiate years

International Journal of Surgical Education

Aim

This review explores the benefits and challenges of a post-college gap year for pre-medical students, while also exploring options for gap-year experiences.

Methods

Our review included peer and non-peer reviewed literature published between 2008 and 2025, online media articles, online content published by medical school consulting companies, official college websites, online discussion forums, online blogs, and YouTube videos.

Results

Post-college gap years carry benefits and challenges and may not be the right choice for every pre-medical student. Potential benefits include more time to fulfill course requirements, time to improve medical school application, more time to save money, time to reflect and recharge, and increased emotional intelligence and maturity. Gap-year challenges include the potential to negatively impact a medical school application, delayed start to medical school, the need to readjust to student life, potential to lose focus, costs, and issues with inequity. Common options for gap years include post-baccalaureate programs, advanced degrees, research, job opportunities, service fellowships, and volunteer options.

Conclusions

Not every pre-medical student will want or need to take a gap year before medical school, and not all gap years are created equal. Therefore, the decision of taking gap years and the choice of what to do during those years should be carefully tailored to the individual needs of a student. While taking a gap year before medical school can be valuable, it is crucial to approach this decision with a clear understanding of the potential benefits and challenges.

INTRODUCTION

Historically the “traditional” path to medical school was a direct one. It often involved matriculating into medical school immediately after completion of their bachelor’s degree. However, with the modern day written and unwritten requirements, many students decide to forgo application and take one or more gap years. According to the 2024 Matriculating Student Questionnaire (MSQ) given by the American Association of Medical Colleges,¹ 74.3% of new incoming matriculants take at least one gap year before starting medical school. Most of them worked at another career (50.2%), worked/volunteered in research (50.0%), or worked to improve their finances (41.3%).¹ Others helped

fulfill family obligations (24.4%), pursued graduate studies (19.2%), continued coursework to fulfill premedical requirements (10.7%), worked/volunteered internationally (8.6%), or took premedical courses for the first time (4.2%).¹ Despite the broad descriptions, these answers provide direction to what medical school admission committees could be looking for. These answers also help outline how prospective medical students can effectively fully utilize their gap year.

In this review, we aim to explore the benefits and challenges of a gap year between college and medical school, as well as identify options for what students may do during their gap years.

Table 1. Benefits and challenges of gap years before medical school.

Benefits	Challenges
Time to fulfill course requirements for medical school application.	Potential negative impact on the medical school application.
Improving medical school application.	Delayed start to medical school.
Saving money.	Readjusting to student life.
Reflecting and recharging.	Potential loss of focus.
Improving emotional intelligence and maturity.	Potential to affect equity in medical school admissions.
Reducing future burnout.	Financial considerations.

METHODS

We conducted a comprehensive review of peer and non-peer reviewed literature published between 2008 and 2024, online media articles, online content published by medical school consulting companies, official college websites, online discussion forums (Reddit, Quora, Student Doctor Network), online blogs, and YouTube videos.

The entire team of authors identified the key literature findings that are summarized in this article. According to VA Boston Healthcare System policy, our literature review study does not require an Institutional Board Review.

RESULTS

Some of the benefits and challenges of taking gap years before medical school are summarized in [Table 1](#).

BENEFITS OF PRE-MEDICAL GAP YEARS

1. TIME TO FULFILL COURSE REQUIREMENTS FOR MEDICAL SCHOOL APPLICATION

In 2024, about 18.5% of matriculating medical students that responded to the MSQ decided to pursue medicine during or after junior year of college.¹ These pre-medical students that may not have had enough time to meet all the pre-requisites for medical school have the option to do a post-baccalaureate program that will allow them to complete the required courses. Students that may have decided to pursue medicine later than most still need to complete biology, physics, and organic chemistry courses to apply to most medical schools.² These post-baccalaureate programs are known as career-changer programs, which fulfill medical school requirements while also providing exposure to high level science courses.³

2. IMPROVING MEDICAL SCHOOL APPLICATION

Students that may have struggled in their undergraduate studies have opportunities to boost their GPA. They may

decide to enroll in a master's program, such as a master's program in public health or medical science. Another option that students may pursue is an "academic enhancer" post-baccalaureate program.^{3,4} These programs are designed for medical school applicants, so there are often opportunities for shadowing, volunteer work, and Medical College Admission Test (MCAT) review.⁵ In practice, these programs are for students who need to bolster their GPA, because these programs can be quite costly. In the 2024-2025 matriculating year, the average GPA of all medical school applicants was 3.66 with the average of all matriculants being 3.79.⁶ Gap years can also give students more time to adequately prepare for the MCAT exams as well as more opportunities and time to network and build relationships that could help them secure stronger letters of recommendation.

Certain post-baccalaureate programs are "linkage programs," which are affiliated with one or more medical schools. Table 2 displays the post-baccalaureate programs with the highest number of linkages and their respective medical school linkages, which were compiled from the AAMC post-baccalaureate program database⁷ and the official websites of each program. Linkages are essentially admission agreements between medical schools and post-baccalaureate programs. However, it does not guarantee admission, but instead provides preferred consideration for admission. Students still need to meet the required MCAT score and GPA for these medical schools. Also, many linkage programs have binding agreements, which limits students to only applying to one linked medical school. Some schools like Washington University in St. Louis look at undergraduate GPA and graduate GPA separately, so academic-enhancer students may not benefit from certain linkage programs.⁸ However, these programs can be incredibly useful if the student has a specific school that they want to attend.

Students may also decide to utilize the gap year to improve on their amount of research or clinical experience. Some common jobs students work to gain clinical experience are as a phlebotomist, emergency medical technician (EMT), medical assistant, or medical scribe.⁹ These jobs all have certifications that can be obtained in less than a year and provide experience with direct patient care. Students that may need more research experience now have time to truly dive deep into a research project and potentially secure a publication.¹⁰ Obtaining a job as a research assistant is one path a pre-medical student may consider post-graduation. In 2021, there were 191,965 research assistant positions in the US.¹¹ Taking a position as a clinical research assistant may also provide clinical experience alongside opportunities to publish. Overall, all these positions provide meaningful experiences that can enhance a student's medical school application.¹²

3. SAVING MONEY

Medical education is expensive, with about 85% of medical school graduates having education debt.¹³ In 2024, the average debt incurred by medical students from medical school and pre-med undergraduate education was

Table 2. Post-baccalaureate programs with the highest number of linkages and their respective linkage medical schools.

Post-Baccalaureate Program	Nr. of linkages	Linkage medical schools
Bryn Mawr College	14	The Warren Alpert Medical School of Brown University; Boston University School of Medicine; Case Western Reserve University School of Medicine; Geisel School of Medicine at Dartmouth; New York University Grossman School of Medicine; Philadelphia College of Osteopathic Medicine; Pritzker School of Medicine at the University of Chicago; Rutgers Robert Wood Johnson Medical School; Sidney Kimmel Medical College at Thomas Jefferson University; SUNY Downstate Medical Center College of Medicine; University of Pennsylvania School of Dental Medicine; University of Pittsburgh School of Medicine; University of Rochester School of Medicine and Dentistry; Weill Cornell Medical College; Zucker School of Medicine at Hofstra/Northwell
Columbia University	13	Columbia University College of Dental Medicine; Columbia University Vagelos College of Physicians and Surgeons; Donald and Barbara Zucker School of Medicine at Hofstra/Northwell; Icahn School of Medicine at Mount Sinai; New York University School of Medicine; Rutgers New Jersey Medical School; SUNY Downstate Medical Center College of Medicine; The Warren Alpert Medical School of Brown University; University of Michigan Medical School; University of Rochester School of Medicine and Dentistry; Weill Cornell Medical College; Ben-Gurion University of the Negev (Israel)
John Hopkins University	7	Boston University School of Medicine; Brown University, Alpert Medical School; Donald and Barbara Zucker School of Medicine at Hofstra/Northwell; New York Institute of Technology, College of Osteopathic Medicine; Rutgers Robert Wood Johnson Medical School; University of Pittsburgh School of Medicine; Weill Cornell Medical School
Scripps College	6	Boston University, School of Medicine; George Washington University, School of Medicine and Health Sciences; Hofstra Northwell School of Medicine; University of Michigan Medical School; University of Pittsburgh School of Medicine; Western University of Health Sciences, College of Osteopathic Medicine
Goucher College	6	University of Chicago Pritzker School of Medicine; The Warren Alpert Medical School of Brown University; Weill Cornell Medical College; University of Pittsburgh School of Medicine; New York University Grossman School of Medicine; Zucker School of Medicine at Hofstra/Northwell
Georgetown University	5	Georgetown University; George Washington University; New York University; Rutgers Robert Wood Johnson; University of Pittsburgh
Eastern Virginia Medical School	4	Eastern Virginia Medical School; Edward Via College of Osteopathic Medicine; West Virginia School of Osteopathic Medicine; Liberty School of Osteopathic Medicine
Temple University	4	George Washington School of Medicine and Health Sciences; Philadelphia College of Osteopathic Medicine; SUNY Downstate Medical Center College of Medicine; Temple University Lewis Katz School of Medicine
Agnes Scott College	4	Mercer University School of Medicine; Morehouse School of Medicine; Philadelphia College of Osteopathic Medicine; Presbyterian College School of Pharmacy.
Tufts University	3	Tufts University School of Medicine; Boston University School of Medicine; UMass Medical School
LaSalle University	2	Robert Wood Johnson Medical School; Philadelphia College of Osteopathic Medicine

\$264,519.¹⁴ This figure also does not include any non-educational debt that students may have, including car loans or medical debt. During their gap years, students could save some money and possibly begin repayment of existing debt to cushion the debt load once medical school begins. Even if a student did not receive any undergraduate debt, it is still beneficial to set aside some money to help cushion the cost of medical school and to take out fewer loans.¹²

4. REFLECTING AND RECHARGING

The pre-medical experience is stressful, and the application process adds another layer of pressure on top of that stress. Premedical students that experience burnout syndrome and depressive symptoms during their undergraduate studies are significantly more likely to depart from the medical career path.¹⁵ Both the competitiveness of a pre-med student’s undergraduate studies and the constant judgement of the student during the application process can have a significant negative impact on a student’s self-image.^{16,17} Taking a gap year provides time for students to mentally reset and rebuild their self-confidence. They may take this time to reconnect with a passion that they may have had to sacrifice while completing their undergraduate degree.¹² Gap years can also provide time to refocus the student’s goal of becoming a doctor. In the process of applying to medical school and being caught up in studying, the endpoint could get lost. The experiences that a student can gain in their gap year can also help reinforce their motivation to become a physician.¹⁸

5. IMPROVING EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND MATURITY

Gap years provide time for students to experience adult life outside of school. This time allows for students to mature and develop their emotional intelligence (EI), defined as the ability for an individual to recognize, understand, and express emotion. EI is a trait that is important not only for patient interaction, but also for working in a team environment. A study done at the University of Manchester¹⁹ compared the ease of transition from classroom learning to clinical rotations between mature and non-mature students. Anyone over the age of 21 at entry to medical school was considered a mature student. The study showed that mature students expressed an easier transition to the clinical environment than non-mature students. In a similar study, the EI of resident physicians that took a gap year before medical school was compared to the EI of those who went straight to medical school from college. This study found that residents that took a gap year before medical school scored higher in interpersonal skills, empathy, decision-making, and impulse control.²⁰

Furthermore, students that work during the gap year may feel more natural in the fast-paced workplace that is a hospital. Even volunteering during a gap year can aid in developing a student’s empathy and professional skills.²¹ EI and maturity form the building blocks of patient-centered care and are integral in forming patient-physician trust.²² Therefore, experiences that aid the development of EI and maturity may improve a student’s chances at getting into

medical school, as well as improving their future quality of care.

6. REDUCING FUTURE BURNOUT

Burnout is a common trait shared among up to 56% of medical students and can potentially lead to future dissatisfaction in medicine.²⁵ Pre-medical students that experience burnout in their undergraduate studies also show a significant reduction in medical career interest.¹⁵ In the cross-sectional study of burnout performed by Guang et al. medical students that took at least one gap year displayed significantly less symptoms of burnout compared to students that did not.²³

CHALLENGES OF PRE-MEDICAL GAP YEARS

1. POTENTIAL NEGATIVE IMPACT ON THE MEDICAL SCHOOL APPLICATION

Gap years should be utilized correctly for them to be beneficial to an applicant. As stated in the AAMC’s guide to gap years, these years are not “time off”.¹² Gap years without an attempt to gain meaningful experience could reflect poorly on a student’s application. Admissions committees may view an unproductive year as a lack of focus and could question an applicant’s commitment to medicine.²⁴ Gap years are not mere vacations, and if the admissions committees cannot identify meaningful experience, then they could assume that there is a lack of commitment.

2. DELAYED START TO MEDICAL SCHOOL

The path to becoming a doctor is a long and arduous road. After graduating high school, it can take between 11-18 years, depending on one’s desired specialty, before practicing as an attending physician.²⁵ This delayed start also means starting residency later, and eventually a later start as an attending physician. Also, there is currently a projected shortage of between 13,500 and 86,000 physicians by 2036.²⁶ Without a gap year, physicians with a 3-year residency will work 36 years on average and physicians with a 7-year residency will work an average of 32 years before retiring.²⁷ Theoretically, each gap year taken reduces the years eventually spent practicing as an attending physician. With the AAMC’s projected shortage of physicians, gap years potentially could have a societal cost. Overall, the length of a medical education and the length of a medical career need to be taken into consideration when deciding whether to take a gap year or not.

3. READJUSTING TO STUDENT LIFE

Some students may see themselves separating from academia during their gap year. The study habits that they have refined and developed during their undergraduate years may not be used during this gap year. For some, they may be able to dive right back into intense studying, but for others it may be a rough transition back into the student life.²⁸ The amount of information that is studied during the first

year of medical school is often equated to drinking from a fire hydrant. Prolonged breaks from studying can make it difficult to adjust to the intense study schedule that is required to succeed in medical school.

4. POTENTIAL LOSS OF FOCUS

Being separated from medicine for an extended period can cause the student to lose sight of the overall goal.²⁸ During this time, students may begin to have doubts about a future in medicine. With the nature of medical school applications, self-doubt can become an obstacle on the path to medicine.¹⁷ In some cases students may find opportunities outside of healthcare that could provide them a stable career. Overall, gap years provide more opportunities for pre-medical students to get distracted from the goal of becoming a physician.

5. POTENTIAL TO AFFECT EQUITY IN MEDICAL SCHOOL ADMISSIONS

The prevalence of gap years before medical school may be contributing to inequity in medical education. Applying to medical school is already a large expense, with the first school fee being \$145 and each subsequent school costing \$46.²⁹ The costs of attaining a medical education already poses a substantial obstacle for low-income applicants. Medical education has historically had an element of elitism that made it difficult for underrepresented minorities to get admitted to medical school. After the Flexner Report was published in 1910, many medical schools that focused on serving impoverished and underserved communities were closed. The shift in priority of medical education transferred to a shift in admission requirements, which put underrepresented students at a disadvantage.³⁰

Financially disadvantaged students may not have the ability to take unpaid research positions or afford an expensive post-baccalaureate program. The opportunities that gap years provide are not necessarily accessible for all pre-medical students. With 74.3% of matriculating medical students in 2024 taking a gap year, the standards for admissions continue to rise.¹ An increased focus on extracurricular activities for admission puts first-generation pre-medical students at a disadvantage because they might have less connections to healthcare.³¹ This could mean less opportunities to shadow, less clinical experience opportunities, and less opportunities for research. All of these are essentially required for admission to medical school, and students that take gap years have significantly more time to pursue these activities. In the 2024 matriculating student questionnaire, 50% of matriculating students that took a gap year used that time to work or volunteer in research.¹ The average salary of a research assistant in 2024 was \$41,414, which is not enough to live comfortably in any major US city, especially if the student needs to support their family financially.^{11,32}

Overall, gap years have become a tool that students use to strengthen their medical school application. However, the growing trend of taking gap years has potentially exac-

erbaded the admission inequity that underrepresented, and financially disadvantaged students faced in the past.

6. FINANCIAL CONSIDERATIONS

Taking gap years before medical school could have both immediate and long-term financial implications that should be considered carefully. Post-baccalaureate or master's programs during gap years are expensive and can add to the overall educational costs. Furthermore, living expenses and potential travel during gap years can be costly.

In the long term, every year postponed is a year of loss of potential earnings, lost retirement savings, and lost career growth. Delaying medical school admission for one or more years could also mean that medical school tuition will likely be more expensive when the student finally matriculates because tuition rates in US universities and colleges usually increase each year at about twice the general inflation rate.³³

GAP YEAR OPTIONS FOR PRE-MEDICAL STUDENTS

Gap years can be incredibly beneficial to a student's medical school application if they decide to use their time strategically. There is a plethora of options for non-traditional students to fulfill course requirements. There are just as many programs designed for students needing to bolster their GPA.

Some students may opt to find a job during their gap year. There are a variety of jobs that pre-medical students can work that will both make them money and help strengthen their medical school application. Increasing clinical hours through either direct patient care or clinical research can help strengthen a pre-medical student's medical school application. For example, becoming an EMT, clinical research assistant, medical scribe, certified nurse assistant, or certified medical assistant can help strengthen an application by exposing the applicant to patient care.³⁴

Students may also want to take time during their gap year to volunteer for a cause they care about. For example, volunteering as a patient ambassador at a Veterans Affairs hospital or helping with public health initiatives at a homeless shelter both do well to strengthen a pre-medical student's application by keeping them connected to healthcare.³⁵ Students may also opt to do longer term volunteering such as the Peace Corps or AmeriCorps. The Peace Corps may be an option for students who wish to travel internationally while also creating a positive impact on the community they serve in. Peace Corps assignments are 2 years of service with 3 months of training. Peace Corps assignments cover a wide variety of subjects including health, education, economic development, youth development, agriculture, and environment.³⁶ Similarly, the AmeriCorps provides service assignments that support the environment, build affordable housing, provide disaster relief, and work alongside various nonprofits to enrich the community. Unlike the Peace Corps, the AmeriCorps service assignments are all based in the US. Each assignment is 10 to 11 months long and consists of various service projects around the country.³⁷ Both the Peace Corps and Ameri-

Corps provide incredible opportunities for students to do good for humanity while also strengthening their medical school application. Importantly, time spent serving as a full-time AmeriCorps or Peace Corps volunteer during gap years counts towards the Public Service Loan Forgiveness requirements.³⁸

A list of selected common gap-year opportunities for pre-medical students is presented in Table 3. Importantly, students can learn about many other available opportunities by connecting with their college's pre-medical advisors and/or alumni.

Regardless of whether the student decides to attend a post-baccalaureate program, get a job, or volunteer, all these options provide meaningful experiences that can strengthen a medical school application. These all have a connection to medicine, whether it be through healthcare-oriented research, direct patient care, or service to others. What is most important is that the student gains meaningful experiences from their gap year that will guide them on their path to becoming physicians.

CONCLUSIONS

Not every pre-medical student will want or need to take a gap year before medical school, and not all gap years are created equal. Pre-medical students need to spend their gap year strategically by participating in activities that specifically strengthen weak points in their application. While improving their application, it is important for students to also take some time for themselves to find an activity that they enjoy doing, pursue a passion, or just unwind and recharge. While taking a gap year before medical school can be valuable, it is crucial to approach this decision with a clear understanding of the potential benefits and challenges.

Editors:

Submitted: March 20, 2025 EDT. Accepted: March 20, 2025 EDT. Published: March 25, 2025 EDT.

Table 3. Common gap-year opportunities for pre-medical students.

Advanced education	Working in healthcare	Research opportunities	Other jobs	Service opportunities	Volunteering
Master's of Science	Medical scribe	Clinical research assistant	Teaching	AmeriCorps	Hospitals
Master's of Medicine	Emergency Medical Technician	Basic science lab research assistant	Healthcare consulting	Peace Corps	Local free clinics
Masters of Public Health	Medical assistant	Research internships	Firefighter	Global Health Corps	Rehabilitation centers
Master's of Public Policy	Nursing assistant	Independent research projects	Tutoring	Teach for America	Hospice
Master's of Global Health	Phlebotomist	Research coordinator	Medical sales representative	City Year	Nursing homes
Other masters programs	Patient care coordinator		Pharmaceutical intern	MedServe	Assisted Living Centers
Post-baccalaureate program	Pharmacy technician		Health insurance analyst	Project Horseshoe Farm	Homeless shelters
Post-baccalaureate internship	Surgical technician		Joining a start-up company	United Nations Foundation	Refugee centers
	Radiology technician		Medical device company	Emerging Leaders Program	Jesuit Volunteer Corps
	Physical therapy assistant			U.S. Schweitzer Fellowship	United Nations
	Laboratory assistant				UNICEF
	Medical billing specialist				Child Family Health International
	Patient liaison				Global Volunteers
	Medical interpreter				Project HOPE
	Home health aide				Volunteers in Medical Missions
	Hospice aide				

REFERENCES

1. 2024 MSQ All Schools Summary Report. AAMC; 2024. <https://www.aamc.org/data-reports/students-residents/interactive-data/2024-msq-all-schools-summary-report>
2. Ahmed A, Boku Y, Korolik E, Shultz B. Premedical Course Requirements in U.S. Medical Schools. *Acad Med*. Published online December 12, 2024. doi:[10.1097/ACM.0000000000005951](https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0000000000005951)
3. Andriole DA, Jeffe DB. Characteristics of medical school matriculants who participated in postbaccalaureate premedical programs. *Acad Med*. 2011;86(2):201-210. doi:[10.1097/ACM.0b013e3182045076](https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0b013e3182045076)
4. Chada S. Should You Take A Gap Year Before Medical School? February 2, 2024. <https://www.ivyscholars.com/should-you-take-a-gap-year-before-medical-school/>
5. A Guide to Record Enhancer Programs. 2025. <https://hpa.princeton.edu/prehealth-after-princeton/postbac-programs/record-enhancement/guide-record-enhancer-programs>
6. 2024 FACTS: Applicants and Matriculants Data Table A-16. AAMC. 2024. <https://www.aamc.org/data-reports/students-residents/data/facts-applicants-and-matriculants>
7. Postbaccalaureate Premedical Programs. AAMC. 2025. <https://mec.aamc.org/postbac/#/index>
8. Post-Bacc Medical School Linkages – What Are They and How Do They Work? April 29, 2019. <https://www.postbaccprogramguide.com/post-bacc-medical-school-linkages-what-are-they-and-how-do-they-work/>
9. Holbrook J. Best Jobs for Premed Students & Gap Year Before Med School. <https://www.stepful.com/post/best-jobs-for-premed-students-and-med-school-gap-year>
10. Pandey A. How to Get Publications from Undergraduate Research. October 13, 2022. <https://medschoolinsiders.com/pre-med/how-to-get-publications-from-undergraduate-research/>
11. Research Assistant Job and Salary Trends Over Time. <https://www.zipppia.com/research-assistant-jobs/trends/>
12. Making the Most of Your Gap Year. AAMC. <https://students-residents.aamc.org/applying-medical-school/making-most-your-gap-year>
13. Mohareb AM, Brown TS. Medical Student Debt and the US Infectious Diseases Workforce. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2023;76(7):1322-1327. doi:[10.1093/cid/ciac862](https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciac862)
14. Hanson M. Average Medical School Debt. August 28, 2024. <https://educationdata.org/average-medical-school-debt>
15. Grace MK. Depressive symptoms, burnout, and declining medical career interest among undergraduate pre-medical students. *Int J Med Educ*. 2018;9:302-308. doi:[10.5116/ijme.5be5.8131](https://doi.org/10.5116/ijme.5be5.8131)
16. Grace MK. Friend or frenemy? Experiential homophily and educational track attrition among premedical students. *Soc Sci Med*. 2018;212:33-42. doi:[10.1016/j.socscimed.2018.07.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2018.07.008)
17. Bynum WE 4th, Jackson JA, Varpio L, Teunissen PW. Shame at the Gates of Medicine: A Hermeneutic Exploration of Premedical Students' Experiences of Shame. *Acad Med*. 2023;98(6):709-716. doi:[10.1097/ACM.0000000000005152](https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0000000000005152)
18. Rashid H, Kibble JD. Understanding reasons for electing gap years between undergraduate education and medical school and the impact of gap years on the student experience of medical education. *Adv Physiol Educ*. 2021;45(4):886-894. doi:[10.1152/advan.00059.2021](https://doi.org/10.1152/advan.00059.2021)
19. Shacklady J, Holmes E, Mason G, Davies I, Dornan T. Maturity, and medical students' ease of transition into the clinical environment. *Med Teach*. 2009;31(7):621-626. doi:[10.1080/01421590802203496](https://doi.org/10.1080/01421590802203496)
20. Shahid R, Adams W. Emotional Intelligence Level Higher in Residents Who Took a Gap Year Before Medical School. *Adv Med Educ Pract*. 2020;11:559-562. doi:[10.2147/AMEP.S268464](https://doi.org/10.2147/AMEP.S268464)
21. Barker ME, Crowfoot G, King J. Empathy development and volunteering for undergraduate healthcare students: A scoping review. *Nurse Educ Today*. 2022;116:105441. doi:[10.1016/j.nedt.2022.105441](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2022.105441)
22. Weng HC. Does the physician's emotional intelligence matter? Impacts of the physician's emotional intelligence on the trust, patient-physician relationship, and satisfaction. *Health Care Manage Rev*. 2008;33(4):280-288. doi:[10.1097/01.HCM.0000318765.52148.b3](https://doi.org/10.1097/01.HCM.0000318765.52148.b3)

23. Guang SA, Eltorai AEM, Durand WM, Daniels AH. Medical student burnout: Impact of the gap year in burnout prevention. *Work*. 2020;66(3):611-616. doi:[10.3233/WOR-203203](https://doi.org/10.3233/WOR-203203)
24. Should You Take a Gap Year Before Medical School? Accessed 2023. <https://www.medschoolcoach.com/gap-years-before-medical-school/>
25. Chan L. How Long It Take To Become a Doctor (For every Specialty). <https://prepformedschool.com/how-long-it-take-to-become-a-doctor-for-every-specialty/>
26. Dall T, Reynolds R, Chakrabarti R, Ruttinger C, Zarek P, Parker O. The Complexities of Physician Supply and Demand: Projections From 2021 to 2036. AAMC. Published online 2024.
27. Allen J. The Downside of the Gap Year Before Medical School. July 12, 2024. <https://hospitalmedicaldirector.com/the-downside-of-the-gap-year-before-medical-school/>
28. Zganiacz P. Taking a Gap year Before Med School (Everything You Should Consider). February 17, 2021. <https://www.medschoolpursuit.com/gap-year-before-med-school/>
29. The Cost of Applying to Medical School. AAMC. August 12, 2024. <https://students-residents.aamc.org/financial-aid-resources/cost-applying-medical-school>
30. Connolly KK, Lee W, Freitas V, Buenconsejo-Lum LE. Historical Inequities in Medical Education - Commitment to Opportunity, Diversity, and Equity at the University of Hawai'i School of Medicine. *Hawaii J Health Soc Welf*. 2024;83(5):138-143. doi:[10.62547/HLHV7741](https://doi.org/10.62547/HLHV7741)
31. Jubbal K. Is Medical School Harder Today Than It Was Back Then? October 8, 2022. <https://medschoolinsiders.com/pre-med/medical-school-today-vs-in-the-past/>
32. Brooks KJ. Here's How Much You Need to Earn to Live Comfortably in Major US Cities. March 7, 2024. <https://www.cbsnews.com/news/salary-income-needed-to-live-comfortably-in-us-cities/>
33. Tuition Inflation. <https://finaid.org/savings/tuition-inflation/#:~:text=A%20good%20rule%20of%20thumb,college%20doubles%20every%20nine%20years>
34. 10 Jobs for Pre-Med Students (With Salaries and Duties). January 15, 2025. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/finding-a-job/jobs-for-premed-students>
35. 40 Clinical Volunteer Opportunities for Pre-Med Students That Will Set You Apart. February 11, 2024. <https://itslifebymaggie.com/clinical-volunteer-opportunities/pre-med/>
36. Our Work Sectors. Peace Corps. <https://www.peacecorps.gov/ways-to-serve/our-work-sectors/>
37. AmeriCorps NCCC. AmeriCorps. <https://americorps.gov/serve/american/american-nccc>
38. Public Service Loan Forgiveness (PSLF). <https://studentaid.gov/manage-loans/forgiveness-cancellation/public-service>